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Inclusive Education And Provision of School Plant As Compensatory Approaches And the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the compensatory approaches as prognosticators of the attainment of sustainable development goal four in public senior secondary schools in rivers state. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The research design was correlation research design. The population of the study was 939 of public senior secondary school principals and vice principals in Rivers state. Using proportionate sampling technique, the sample size drawn was 520 principals and vice principals. Data were collected using two self-structured questionnaires titled components of Compensatory Approaches Questionnaire (CCAQ) and Attainment of sustainable development goal four Questionnaire (ASDG4Q) with 40 items. The reliability index was obtained using Cronbach alpha was 0.85 and 0, 81. Data was analyzed using simple regression to answer the research questions while the T- Test associated with simple regression was used to answer research hypotheses. Some findings of the study were that the Compensatory Approaches showed that inclusive education had a high positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four with 56.7% also that provision of school plant has a low positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four with 38.5%.Based on the findings, recommendations made were: The government should monitor the implementation of inclusive education in schools and provision of school plants for the realization of the attainment of sustainable development goal four. Conclusively, compensatory approaches jointly will provide the anticipated attainment of sustainable development goal four in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Keywords: compensatory approach, attainment of sustainable development goal four, Inclusive education and provision of school plant.

INTRODUCTION

Education embodies the act of teaching or training. It involves the acquisition of knowledge, skills, ability through impartation and the development of rare skills that initiates productivity which profits the recipient and the society at large. Nwafor (2016) opined that education is an enterprise to which an individual devotes part of his time, with a view to producing desirable change in the learner. Also, education means specific information of thought, feeling and action distinct from mere socialization. Education is as essential to existence as oxygen is to life (Lawal, et al., 2021). It is also one of the most significant components of human assets since it provides knowledge and skills that enable

individuals to be responsible and self-sufficient. The process of assisting learning, or the acquisition of information, skills, values, morals, beliefs, habits, and personal growth, is known as education.

One of the goals of education is the development of critical reflective agents. An uneducated nation will remain ignorant and stagnant. Therefore every nation should strive at creating an educated public that is independent and can construct their own development. The only people to drive the society out of the pool of ignorance are the teachers “A teacher is a ladder towards independent thinking” (Salaami, 2022). Exponents of Education have analyzed the concept of teaching and have essayed that teaching denotes action undertaken with the intention of bringing about learning in another individual. In this way, teaching is distinguished from mere telling or showing; it involves a face to face encounter in which the teacher’s actions are conducive to bringing about student’s learning.

Education is “a cumulative process of development of intellectual abilities, skills and attitudes, all of which form our various outlooks and dispositions to action in life generally”. It is the pristine essence of learning which makes us permanently able and disposed to benefit ourselves and other members of the society in the way we make use of such learning. Education, broadly speaking consists of all the influence involved in shaping the development of an individual. It influences one’s behaviour (Adesemowo, 2022). Although, certain attributes may be acquired through negative learning and an individual may succeed in carrying out a negative, anti-social behaviour like “pen-robbery”, armed robbery, examination malpractices, raping and many more; for one’s behaviour to have educational worth, it must be positive (Sotonade, 2022). Thus, the whole life of an individual’s education and it ceases when one dies.

According to Ogbondah (2016), education is the process by which every society attempts to preserve and upgrade the accumulated knowledge, skills and attitudes in its cultural setting and heritage in order to foster and guarantee its survival. It is also the means by which we transmit culture, norms, tradition, rules from one generation to the other and this is done so that the society can continue to exist. The idea of education in any developing country which has undergone a colonial experience in terms of the transmission of culture should be different from that of a country that has not got this experience (Adeniji, 2022). Hence in the transmission of culture in the developing country, it must not constitute only the alien culture but also the indigenous culture. This means that education is a vital tool through which society uses schools, colleges, universities and other institutions deliberately to transmit societal values, norms and cultural heritage to the younger ones.

The educated person must be able to adjust himself to any environment as education is sometimes referred to as imitation in the sense that anybody that comes into society does not know the norms and the other essential things to be known in a society. The only way to do this is by imitation (Omoniyi, 2022). Education is being regarded therefore as a veritable tool for inculcating in the individual the skills, abilities, aptitudes, attitudes, interest, values and skills which are necessary for functioning effectively in the society. Arikewuyo (2022) stated that education is also essential for salvaging virtues of all shades in a way that is beneficial to the society.

Therefore, education is the most important tool for empowering individuals in every community. It is the basis for lifelong learning and human growth (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). According to United Nations Children’s Fund (2022), every child, regardless of where they live or their circumstances, has the right to quality education. Unfortunately, the education system in Nigeria has not kept up with the country’s fast rising school-age population. Both basic education and secondary education in the country is of inadequate quality, resulting in low demand and unacceptable academic achievement (United States Agency for International Development, USAID, 2021). About 10 million of the country’s 30 million school-aged children are anticipated to be enrolled in fully recognized schools. Less than a third of primary school students will go on to junior high school, and even fewer will go on to senior secondary school. Today, education is hampered by a lot of problems which tends to deprive the Nigerian child and make him/her under privileged or educationally disadvantaged.

Secondary education is a crucial tier in the hierarchy of education in Nigeria. It is the budding ground for future professionals as well as the foundation for the discovering and classification of the specific fields of professions. Prior to the independence of Nigeria through to 1982, Secondary Education lasted only five years (Tatbotndip, 2020). After the duration of five years, those who obtained the required qualifications were allowed for the two years of Higher School Certificate which qualifies them for university education. Thus the system allowed for three years junior and two years senior.

However, discovering the need to enhance this tier of education with science and technical subjects, the curriculum was broadened to have its duration extended to six years. The importance of this stage of education cannot be over-emphasized. The certificate for the junior secondary school was based on a continuous assessment while the senior secondary certificate was issued after writing a national examination (The West African Council Examination-WAEC). Today, there is another body that conducts similar examination at the end of the six year duration independent of WAEC; The National Examination Council Examination (NECO) (Nanbak, 2020). Some of the Cardinal objectives for which secondary education was established in Nigeria are The provision of smooth opportunities for primary school leavers to further acquire higher quality education irrespective of their sex, religion, social and ethnic backgrounds., To diversify its curriculum to cater for the variety of talents that is latent in the students to come to light in a productive way, To equip the students with the relevant scientific and technical knowledge to effectively survive in the modern age, To foster national unity with emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity and to inspire students with a high desire for achievement and self-improvement both at school and in later life.

It is very significant that these ideals are set for attainment of quality education within the secondary system. Secondary education serves as the bridge between primary and tertiary institutions and thus holds the compass for the direction the nation intends to follow. It is therefore understandable to maintain that the failure of this tier of education poses a damaging threat to the nation at large. The Federal Governments at different times has somehow left this tier of education chiefly in the hands of state Governments and voluntary agencies as well as private individuals. The pitiable condition of the secondary education sector is further dampened by the Federal government's inability to come up with a standing policy guiding the advancement of the schools. Lack of policy statement on this burning issue has further demonstrated that the Federal Government lacks either the political will to mediate and proffer lasting solutions or that it is tacitly comfortable with the deterioration of this sector of education (Sulaimano, 2019). According to Nanbak (2020), This calls for a rethinking and reappraisal of the status quo. A look at the above discrepancies as evidenced in the state to state administration of the secondary sectors shows that, if the said objectives are to be achieved, we need to tow a different line of approach, a compensatory approach in addressing the problems.

The federal government should create opportunities where strategies and styles of management would be brought to the common table for a review. Thus, instead of making progressive steps, we are rather retrogressing. In the light of this, government and all stake holders in this sector of education should discourage making references to the achievements made in the past and explore newer levels of progress. We are to challenge teachers and students alike to be at their best in order to excel beyond their predecessors. Consequently, as a means to revive the strong will of commitment, several new policies and approaches thrust should be developed to encourage stakeholders to spring into action to revive the almost decayed secondary sector. On this, government must exhibit the strong will to remain resolute towards ensuring that the implementation of these approaches is carried out asymmetrically.

Concept of Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted by the United Nation's one hundred and ninety three (193) member states at the historic United Nations General Assembly Summit that held in September 2015. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted were Seventeen (17) and their 169 targets were part of this agenda. These Sustainable Development Goals are bold, universal agreement to end poverty and all its dimensions. They are geared towards the ability to craft an equal, just and secure world – for people, planet and prosperity. The SDGs have been developed through an unparalleled consultative process that brought national governments and millions of citizens from the globe together to negotiate and adopt this ambitious agenda. According to Bizikova, Denton and Pinter (2022), the universal nature of the SDGs implies that countries should clean up their own act and contribute to helping others to do so; but it also implies that their action must be commensurate with the extent to which they are part of the problem.

The 5P's of Sustainable Development Goals: Which are Planet, People, Prosperity, Peace and partnership. The progress on one P must balance and support the progress on another. The 17 SDGs are structured around the five pillars of the 2030 Agenda. These 5 Ps highlight how the SDGs are an intertwined framework instead of a group of solo goals.

People: This is the fostering of inclusion. Member countries are shown the need to curb inequality that exists among people. It also words towards the desire to end poverty and hunger in all forms. The UNDP (2022) observed that the focus of SDGs on people is to ensure dignity, equality and fulfilling lives in harmony with nature. Also to promote policies on inequality issues and gender issues in country. The SGDs on ending poverty, hunger, allowing individuals to have good health and well-being, provision of quality education, access to clean water and sanitation, and striving for gender equality surround the broad ambit of people. The SDGs is committed to providing an enabling environment for improving the lives of people, as a collective and on an individual level. It further strives to synergize the public and private efforts, geared to end poverty and hunger in diverse forms and dimensions, ensuring dignity and equality take precedence for all and in a healthy environment.

Prosperity: the SDGs aim at supporting growth, provisions of jobs, and poverty reduction as this will foster peaceful, just and inclusive societies. According to the Punjab SDGs Unit (2023), Inequality is one of the defining issues of this generation and requires a commensurate focus that to date is still lacking. Ensuring prosperous and fulfilling lives in harmony with nature embodies the kind of prosperity the world must look to strive for in the next ten years. Conscientious attempts must be made to support the provincial and district governments in aligning their planning and budgetary instruments with SDGs and leverage the private sector initiatives and mobilize their resources for reduced inequality, shared prosperity, and sustainable development.

Planet: Climate Change is a roadblock to achieving the SDGs and has disproportionate effects on the poor. Without concerted action, it could drive 100 million more people into poverty by 2030. Therefore the SDGs were created to encourage member countries to engage in actions that will promote a healthy climate by protecting our planet's natural resources and climate for the future generations. Also by adapting to climate change and understanding the financial implications of global climate change. The SDGs are geared to pursue and to accelerate the on-ground efforts and create increased awareness on producing clean and affordable energy, protecting life on both lands and in the sea, taking demonstrable actions to prevent climate change, and learning to produce and consume as responsibly as possible (Punjab SDGs Unit, 2023).

Peace: the SDGs are made for strengthening institutions and governance by tackling corruption and shining a bright light into the dark corners of weak governance and corruption. They also foster the building of fiscal capacity in fragile states and implement the agenda through solid global partnership. Justice underpins the success of the SDGs: from ending poverty and inequality to ensuring no one is left behind. The world is still a long way away from becoming peaceful, but only through consciously working towards this goal can we make any progress in preventing violence and making communities more secure from top to bottom. The SDGs creates a holistic approach that fosters peaceful, just and inclusive societies (UNDP, 2023). It upholds the vision to provide all segments of society, especially women, minorities, and other vulnerable segments with a conducive environment, where they can have fair, equitable, and inclusive access to the available resources for sustainable development.

Partnership: this is important as it encapsulates the financing the 17SDGs. Partnership is achieved through the creation Mainstreaming, Acceleration, and Policy Support (MAPS) for each SDG. The need to sensitize all public and private stakeholders to own, implement, and accelerate SDGs in their respective capacities is imperative. According to The Punjab SDGs Support Unit (2023) realizing this need and it strives to create an enabling environment for diverse stakeholders, helping them build partnerships to mobilize resources and identify innovative solutions to accelerate progress on the prioritized SDGs.

However for the purpose of this study, the attentiveness shall be on Quality Education which is the Fourth Sustainable Development Goal. This fourth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG4) is concerned with everything that will lead to the development and growth in education in nations that are members of the United Nations. The triumph of SDG4 is the capability to guarantee inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. It plays a central role in building sustainable, inclusive and resilient societies. Hence the significance of quality education encapsulated in SDG4 cannot be overemphasized as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is universal, holistic and indivisible, with a special imperative to leave no one behind. The real essence of the SDGs as established by over 190 countries who are member nations of the United Nations at a

global summit in September 2015 is to ensure that there is an attainable and prosperous plan of action for people and the planet (Assembly, 2015).

Fundamentally, this resolve came into focus as a result of the enormous global crisis posed by poverty that was engulfing the nations. For this reason, the United Nations in accord with its over 190 member nations alongside civil organizations averred that eradicating poverty in all its forms and dimensions is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development. The seventeen (17) SDGs were devised to stimulate action over the next ten years in areas affecting humanity and the planet in various forms and dimensions with greater emphasis on tackling extreme poverty which has assumed the position of a perennial global challenge and an imperative requirement to be addressed for sustainable development (Ávila et al, 2022). Hence, all countries and all stakeholders in the United Nations General Assembly are acting in collaborative partnership to implement these plans/ goals that will be the much needed tool for liberating the human race from the tyranny of poverty. Out of these 17 SDGs, only SDG4 is solely burdened with the task of healing and securing the planet through quality education (Assembly, 2015)

According to Hanemann (2019), it is worthy to note that out of all 169 targets of SDGs, SDG 4 consists of 10 targets and 12 indicators. Eight of these SDG 4 indicators are supposed to be achieved by 2030, while one is to be achieved by 2020 and the rest have no target years. Each of the targets has one or more indicators to measure the progress made in achieving quality education (Gennari, & D'Orazio, 2020).The ten (10) targets of SDG4 include: Free secondary education, Equal access to quality pre-primary education, Equal access to affordable technical, Vocational and higher education, Increase the number of people with relevant skills for financial success, Elimination of all discrimination in education, Advancement of universal literacy and numeracy, Enhancement of education for sustainable development and global citizenship, building and upgrading of inclusive and safe schools, Expanding higher education scholarships for developing countries and Increase in the supply of qualified teachers in developing countries.

The concept of the SDG 4 targets is determined by its strongly orientated position towards various benchmarks and indicators (Boeren, 2019). Cardoso and Steiner-Khamsi (2017), observed that this has become more pronounced because other global organizations besides the United Nations such as the World Bank, European Commission and the organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) have the capacity to influence the existing policy on education to conform to the current reality and future projections through the collection, monitoring and publication of statistics supporting a pre-defined set of targets. Since the inception of SDGs in 2015, the European Commission has been publishing annual monitoring reports as part of its strategic framework entitled "Education and Training 2020", for which it formulated a set of benchmarks to be achieved by 2020 (Boeren,2019; Council of the European Union/European Commission, 2015). Parts of the dimensions deduced from this annual publication comprised: early school leaving; higher education completion, basic skills, early childhood education, lifelong learning; transition to the labour market; and mobility between countries (Brooks, 2018).

Similarly, the organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has also been involved in publishing annual "Education at a Glance" report, providing statistics on the current state of education around the world. Areas covered by the OECD reports are: the output of educational institutions and the impact of learning; financial and human resources invested in education; access to education, participation and progression; and the learning environment and organization of schools. This is in tandem with the resolution of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that included target which averred that countries should provide every child with access to free secondary education by 2030.

Concerns about the ability of low income countries to meet these targets led to the formation of the International Commission on Financing Global Education in 2015. Also there are new knowledge horizons and opportunities for strengthened solidarity and partnerships around the provision of quality education and lifelong learning for all. There are many barriers to the access of quality education and educational outcomes remain a challenge to monitor such as ever changing new technologies and skill demands, as well as economic shocks and environmental degradation (Niewöhner, 2022). Therefore in order to properly monitor the attainment of SDG4 targets we must crucially consider practical ways to

improve access to quality education and lifelong learning and deliver genuine impact both on people and sustainable development

Targets can be scaled up or replicated for success to ensure that no one is left behind in accessing quality education. By facilitating teacher's training, countries can monitor targets that improve the quality of education and ensure better learning outcomes. Also by making sure that learning systems are changed to match a rapidly changing world due to technological shifts, global integration and climate pressures.

There has been wide-range of advancements in the development and measurement of SDG 4 and its 10 targets covering 11 global and 12 thematic indicators. The UNESCO Institute for Statistics continues to lead the development of clearly defined, valid, and internationally comparable data with broad geographical coverage. Yet, challenges to the monitoring of SDG 4 progress remains. Among others, these include incomplete methodological development; limited data availability in many countries and regions and on various sources of information including on the nature of inter linkages between education and other goals and insufficient funding both for countries (Schoon, 2022). Efforts to improve monitoring of and reporting on inequalities in education are being made through the WIDE (World Inequality Database on Education) platform.

There are global trends already affecting individual lives and may do so for decades to come unless steered with a purpose, the rapid advance of science and technology may widen inequities, exacerbate social fragmentation and accelerate resource depletion. These have triggered a global debate on the impact of education to every country and have given rise to the call for global and local solutions. This is the reason SDG 4 sets specific targets to address these challenges and provides a comprehensive framework in order to achieve inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Beyond enrolment rates, SDG 4 puts a welcomed emphasis on quality education and learning outcomes. The targets cover lifelong education from early childhood development to university and vocational training. Special attention is also given to eliminating gender disparities and ensuring equal access to education for vulnerable children (Billett, 2019).

The following breakdown of each SDG 4 target provides an insight into the current global situation on education and reveals the pressures and issues relevant to the achievement of each target. The targets are:

Target 1: To ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and SDG 4 effective learning outcomes: According to UNESCO (2022), the indicator for this target is defined as the proportion of children and young people achieving at least a minimum proficiency level in reading and mathematics. The global primary school net enrolment rate was 89.41% in 2018, with little progress in the last ten years, reflecting pockets of exclusion and hard-to-reach populations. The secondary school net enrolment rate was 66.27% in 2018. There is still a lot of room for improvement regarding the school completion rate. Even though 81% of children are in school in sub-Saharan Africa, just 63% complete primary education. This situation is even worse for lower secondary education, where 63% of children aged 12-14 years enrol in school, but only 38% complete it (Auld, Rappleye, & Morris, 2019). To provide a more accurate view of the education situation, the UNESCO Institute for Statistics has combined 'enrolment and completion indicators with SDG Indicator 4.1.1 to produce a quality-adjusted enrolment and completion rate'. This statistic covers the physical state, social-emotional development, learning approaches and literacy-numeracy skills of children. The availability of country-specific data is low, with only 66 countries providing data. On average, 76% of 3 to 4-year-olds in the countries that have disclosed data are developmentally on track. Remaining challenges include malnutrition, difficult home environments and lack of access to early childhood care and education.

Target 2: By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education: Two indicators are used to measure success for this target. The first indicator covers the proportion of under 5-year-olds that are developmentally on track in health, learning and psychosocial well-being. Only recently, in March 2019, the Inter-Agency and Expert Group on SDG Indicators agreed on a methodology to assess early childhood development. Until this methodology is generally adopted, the achievements for target 4.2 can only be accessed through the UNICEF Early Childhood Development Index (ECDI). The ECDI framework is a common benchmark that links existing learning assessment studies.

Secondly, due to their restrictive nature, indicators are unable to measure all dimensions comprehensively. As universal education expands, the learning outcomes may decrease initially since the education system needs time to adjust to more disadvantaged students.

In its Information Paper, the UNESCO Institute for Statistics highlights the example of Indonesia, where the proportion of 15-year-olds achieving a minimum proficiency in science fell by 5% within 6 years while the number of 15-year-old students increased by 12% at the same time.²⁵ Overall, the amount of children in that age group who were in school and achieved the minimum proficiency increased, while the value for the indicator actually declined. To provide a more accurate view of the education situation, the UNESCO Institute for Statistics has combined enrolment and completion indicators with SDG Indicator 4.2 to produce a quality-adjusted enrolment and completion rate. This covers the physical state, social-emotional development, learning approaches and literacy-numeracy skills of children. However, the rate varies widely between 42% in low-income countries and 93% in high income countries. Pre-pandemic projections predicted that the global share of children who attend organised learning one year before the official primary entry age would reach 82% in 2030. UNESCO Report noted that only 50 out of countries and territories had compulsory pre-primary education and 38 countries had free and compulsory pre-primary education.

Target 3: By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university. This target calls for equal access to lifelong learning beyond compulsory education. It encompasses formal and non-formal education for youth and adults for work and non-work purposes. The global gross enrolment ratio in tertiary education reached 38% in 2018. However, it ranges vastly from 9% in low-income countries, to 75% in high-income countries. In these two income groups, the numbers have only marginally changed in the past ten years. The biggest improvements can be observed in middle-income and upper-middle income countries, in East Asia and the Pacific, where the gross enrolment ratio increased by over 10% between 2013 and 2018. The total global enrolment in secondary vocational education reached 62.5mn in 2018, a number which is slowly starting to increase again after having dropped, following a peak at over 65 million in 2013.

Target 4: By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship: The indicator agreed for this target focuses on Information and Communications Technology (ICT) skills. The rationale being that it measures skills beyond literacy and numeracy that are highly important for today's working world around the globe. Additionally, it invites States to offer ICT education in and outside school. To measure the proportion of youth and adults mastering these skills, individuals are asked through household surveys whether they have carried out nine specific digital activities in the last three months. According to a household survey carried out by the International Telecommunication Union in 2021, one in three participants in middle-income countries copied or moved a file or folder in the last three months, compared to two in three in high-income countries. The skill that was used the least of the nine computer skills surveyed was programming, with a global average of only 5% of people having programmed in the last three months.

Generally, data coverage is insufficient outside high-income countries. In addition to the difficulties of collecting enough data, this indicator has suffered criticism for solely focusing on ICT skills. At the moment, there is no indicator capturing financial literacy skills and attempts to capture social-emotional skills remain challenging, although these skills constitute key competences for employment as well.

Target 5: By 2030, to eliminate gender disparities in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for the vulnerable, including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples and children in vulnerable situations: Measurement of progress towards this target involves comparing education indicators for different groups (female/male, urban/rural, richest/poor and disability status) that would have an impact on an individual's ability to access quality education. This will be done as the data becomes available. The greatest challenge for achieving equitable education appears to be disparities in wealth. A recent assessment showed that inequity constitutes a major challenge, with children from the richest 20% of households achieving greater proficiency in reading than those from the poorest households. According to the Global Education Monitoring Report from 2022, rural students in low- and middle-income countries are 50% less likely to complete upper

secondary education compared to urban students. In light of the COVID-19 pandemic, disparities in wealth have played a major factor in influencing how well the schools and the learners responded to the closure of schools.

As far as gender is concerned, although the overall rate of girls that are out-of-school is higher, the female students who are in school have better reading proficiency than their male counterparts. In 2022, gender parity was achieved in terms of the global average enrolment rates up to secondary education. Excluding primary education in sub-Saharan Africa, there was also gender parity on average in all regions in primary and lower secondary education. However, only 24% of all countries reached gender parity in upper-secondary education. Notably, reduced access of women and girls to technology during the pandemic has further restricted girls' access to education.

Although the SDG Agenda pledges to 'leave no one behind' and this target calls for equal access to education for all children, it is concerning that this target and its indicators are silent on some of the most important factors of discrimination, especially race and ethnicity, which have historically barred many children from accessing quality education. UNESCO's 2020 report on Inclusion and Education, stated, 'Laws and policies set the framework for achieving inclusion in education. The links between racial inequalities and unequal access to quality education persist today and addressing these disparities should be central to efforts to deliver quality education for all.

Target 6: By 2030, ensure that all youth and a substantial proportion of adults, both men and women, achieve literacy and numeracy: In 2018, the youth (aged 15-24) literacy rate for men was 92.9%, compared to 90.4% for women. For adults (aged 15+), the literacy rate for men was 89.8% in 2018, compared to 82.8% for women. With an adult literacy rate of 65.6%, Sub-Saharan Africa lays more than 20% behind the global average. Incessant school closures have severely impacted literacy rates, with gains made over the last 20 years being wiped out for children in grades 1-8.

Target 7: By 2030, ensure that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development: This is arguably the most challenging target to interpret and measure, as such outcome orientated wording is hard to define globally. At the moment, the indicator for target describes the circumstances required for sustainable development, human rights and global citizenship education by measuring the extent to which global citizenship and education for sustainable development, including gender equality and human rights, are mainstreamed into national education policies, curricula, teacher education and student assessment.

There are no internationally established methodologies or standards available for this target and there is very limited data on which to judge progress made. The UNESCO recommendation concerning Education for International Understanding, Co-operation and Peace; Education relating to Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms is used to measure the success of target. In the sixth consultation round in 2016, 83 countries submitted reports about implementation of the Recommendation's guiding principles in their education system. Almost 60% of the countries reported that the Recommendation had been 'fully reflected' in national education policies and in more than 80% of the countries, student assessments had included the principles.

However, only 17% of these countries reported that working teachers received education that fully reflect the Recommendation and teaching hours dedicated to the principles were not fully sufficient in 79% of the countries. UNESCO described target as providing learners with the knowledge and competencies they need to make all the SDGs a reality. Education plays a fundamental role in the achievement of sustainable development, as it raises awareness of global issues and provides individuals with the essential skills and knowledge to act upon them. Therefore, SDG can be considered a critical goal on its own and as an enabler of other SDGs. Hence, it ensures the overall success of Agenda 2030 like no other target. The targets are considered supportive targets. These are targets that give the prospect and road map towards achieving other targets in SDG4. When practised astutely they create the opportunity for inclusivity and improved quality education for all.

Target 8: Create effective learning environments: This can be achieved by building and upgrading education facilities that are child, disability and gender sensitive, In addition to making the environment safe, non-violent, inclusive and equipped for effective learning for all.

Target 9: Award Scholarships: By 2020, substantially expand globally the number of scholarships available to developing countries, in particular least developed countries, island, developing States and African countries. Scholarships should be awarded to individuals that desire to enrol into higher education, including vocational training and information and communications technology, technical, engineering and scientific programmes in developed countries and other developing countries.

Target 10: Supply and train teachers and educators: By 2030, substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially least developed countries and Small Islands.

Fig. 2.2: Targets of Attainment of sustainable development goal four
Source: Researcher’s Idea

Today, educational system in Nigeria is guided by the broad National objectives which are articulated in the National Policy on Education. In 2004, the challenges faced in the primary education sector, moved the Fourth Republic administration to launch the Universal Basic Education Programmeme. The Universal Basic Education Act (2004) and the Child Rights Act provide the legal framework for the implementation of the Programmeme, which makes basic education not only free and accessible but also compulsory. Presently, various efforts and programmes are available to help compensate the deprived based on the type of deprivation so as to provide equal educational opportunities to all. Noteworthy is the fact that compensatory approach to education is not limited to the child inside the educational institution, but efforts are also directed toward an improvement of the environment, so that the entire community and families therein may be deeply involved. Borman (2022) observed that the idea behind compensatory approach is in a sense to “compensate” for the disadvantaged by expanding and improving the educational programmes offered to children living in poverty. This view supports the idea of Pringle (2015) who opined that poverty is a major cause of deprivation.

Therefore, the attainment of quality education (SDG4) is directly related to the ability of an administrator to identify and vanquish these deprivations to enable children get the best education because being in school is not enough if they are not learning (Atkin, 2022). Educational deprivation in the light of the above definition means to deny a child opportunity to gain education. Education deprivation can also be regarded as being educationally disadvantaged, education imbalance and education inequality among individuals (Osimini, Amopho & Ugwu, 2020).According to Gregg (2022) deprivation can have a large and pervasive impact on education attainment even when the student is back to school. He explained that education is usually thought of in terms of what schools are aiming to provide but noted that the success of a child within the formal setting depends almost entirely on the success of the informal learning has being in the preceding years. Therefore, the child

who grows up in a home which is not culturally and educationally stimulating is handicapped by environment deprivation; the child who is unloved by the parents suffers emotional/psychological deprivation; and the child who lives in residential care for a long period or permanently is deprived from normal family life and all these have great impact on how the child perceives education (Pringle, 2015). Frost and Rowland (2003) opined that deprivation was a major concern of President Johnson of America: To this Johnson carried out an antipoverty crusade that drafted a proposal to congress in 1964 to bring relief to depressed areas. In Nigeria in general and Rivers State in particular, there exist obvious educational inequalities in various parts of the state. This can be traced to different historical, social, religious background and ideologies during the colonial and post-colonial Nigeria (Patrick, 2022). There are various types of educational deprivation that definitely inhibit the attainment of SDG4 in Rivers State and Nigeria at large.

Concept of Compensatory Approaches

Generally, compensatory approach can be defined as strategies used to help people perform tasks in an alternative manner or by using adaptive aids so that they can be more independent. Compensatory approach also helps people learn new tasks and enables them to perform assigned job tasks with increased independence. Hence, in educational administration, compensatory approach are measures aimed at identifying new ways to perform assigned tasks with increased independence that will lead to improved quality of education. Compensatory approaches in education are all educational measures aimed at helping both children and adults who are educationally disadvantaged or deprived to benefit more fully in formal education. Compensatory approaches in education can be defined as educational measures aimed at addressing disparity in society caused by deprivation (Osimini, Amopho and Ugwu, 2022). Compensatory approach in education serves as supplementary education and programmes designed to repositioning the disadvantaged child. Also it serves as a re-awaken educational and economic strategy for the under privileged.

The concept of compensatory education was born out of the international Human Right for equality in obtaining quality education. These include the universal declaration of human rights (1948), the international covenant on economic, social and cultural rights (1966) and the African charter on human and peoples' right (1981). The universal declaration of human rights was adopted and proclaimed by the United States general assembly on December 10, 1948, which states "as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, to the end that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to secure their universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the people of member states themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction".

This declaration consists of a preamble and 30 articles, setting forth the Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms to which all men and women, everywhere in the world, are entitled, without any discrimination. Article 1, upon which the philosophy and declaration is laid, reads: "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood". Article 2, which sets out the basic principles of equality and non-discrimination as regards the enjoyment of Human Rights and fundamental freedoms, forbids "distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status". Article 3, proclaims the right to life, liberty and security of person, as a cornerstone of the declaration, which are essential rights to the enjoyment of all other rights. It introduces the series of Articles (Articles 4 to 21) in which the human rights of every individual are explained in details further (Olanami, 2017).

To this study the article of interest is Article 26 which states that, everyone has the right to education and free education to at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. This declaration triggered Africa as a continent to consider the United Nations declaration in the eighteenth conference of states and government of the OAU which held in June 1981 at Nairobi, Kenya. This led to the draft of the African Charter of Human and People's Rights to promote freedom, equality, justice and dignity among Africans. Also, article 28 of the United Nations convention on the Rights of the Child, gave state parties the responsibility to recognize the right of the child to education. Therefore, the attainment of quality education (SDG4) is directly related to the ability of an administrator to identify and

vanquish these deprivations to enable children get the best education because being in school is not enough if they are not learning (Atkin, 2022).

Statement of the problem

Some of the problems responsible for the students deprivations to quality education include; insufficient budgetary allocation, malfunctioning school plant facilities, inconsistent educational policies, shortage of teaching materials and insufficient quality teachers. Therefore inventive and critical thinking that will lead to creating strategies and approaches is a must for secondary school administration. These compensatory approaches will guide the administrator towards meeting the global demand for quality education thereby making education affordable and accessible to all. However, the head of most of the secondary schools are very much conversant with limitations such as lack of free education, free transportation, free school meal, remedial education, award of scholarship, poor implementation of inclusive education and provision of school plant facilities that pose a threat to the attainment of quality education by the year 2030 as stipulated in sustainable development goal four.

Therefore the researcher was burdened with the following questions: are there alternative ways and approaches that can lead to improved quality education? Can the swift attainment of sustainable development goal four be made a reality through the implementation of compensatory approaches? Can more than one compensatory approaches be utilized, implemented and replicated at the same time for effective results towards the attainment of sustainable development goal four in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study examined compensatory approaches and attainment of sustainable development goal four (SDG4) in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. The objectives sought to:

1. determine the extent to which inclusive education programmes predicts Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent to which provision of school plant facilities predicts Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do inclusive education programmes predict Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State?
2. To what extent do provision of school plant facilities predict Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

1. Inclusive education programmes do not significantly predict Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State.
2. School plant facilities do not significantly predict Attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the Correlational research design. In this study the dependent variable is Attainment of sustainable development goal four (SDG4) and independent variables are free education and free transportation. The population of the study comprised of the 939 principals and vice principals in 313 public secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample of this study comprised 520 Principals and vice principals in the public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique was used for the study. The research instrument utilized for data collection in this study was two sets of self-structured questionnaires; Compensatory Approach Questionnaire (CAQ) and Attainment of sustainable development goal four Questionnaire (ASDG4Q) with 90 items in all.

The questionnaire items was arranged in the modified 4 point Likert rating scale which are Very High Extent (VHE)= 4, High Extent (HE)=3, Low Extent (LE)=2 and Very Low Extent (VLE)= 1. 520

copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents. Respondents were given some time to respond to the statements and were collected on the spot. Out of 520 copies administered, 509 copies were properly filled and retrieved representing 98% success. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions 1-7 while multiple regression was used to answer research question eight. On the other hand, t-test associate with simple regression was used to test hypotheses 1-7 while ANOVA associated with multiple regression was used to test hypotheses eight at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis and Empirical Results

Research Question 1: *To what extent does inclusive education predict attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 6: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Inclusive Education Programmes Predict Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.753	.567	.348	High Extent

Table 1 revealed that the R was .753 while R square and adjusted R square were .567 and .348 respectively. The coefficient determinism was calculated to be 56.7% (.567 x 100). This means that to a high extent inclusive education programme predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four with 56.7%. By implication, this showed that inclusive education programme has a high positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four. This implies that full implementation of inclusive education programme will lead to achievement of attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do provision of school plant facilities predict attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Provision of School Plant Facilities Predict Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Decision
1	.621	.385	.322	Low Extent

Table 2 revealed that the R was .621 while R square and adjusted R square were .36 and .322 respectively. The coefficient determinism was calculated to be 38.5% (.385 x 100). This means that to a low extent provision of school plant facilities predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four with 38.5%. By implication, this showed that provision of school plant facilities have a low positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four. This implies that improvement in provision of school plant facilities leads to attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Inclusive education programme does not significantly predict attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: T-test Associated with Simple Regression on Prediction of Inclusive Education Programme on Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Alpha Level	t	Probability value	Remark
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	Inclusive education programme	3.853	2.112		0.05	1.717	.244	Hypothesis is rejected
	2	attainment of sustainable development goal four	.863	.061				

Table 3 revealed that the probability value of .000 ($p < 0.05$) is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore the hypothesis is rejected. This implied that inclusive education programme significantly predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Hypothesis 2: Provision of school plant facilities do not significantly predict attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: T-test Associated with Simple Regression on Prediction of Provision of School Plant Facilities on Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	P-Val	Alpha level	Remark
		B	Std Error	Beta				
Provision of school plant facilities attainment of sustainable development goal four	of	3.334	2.165		1.034	.000	0.05	Hypothesis is rejected
	of	1.022	.331	.621				

Table 4 revealed that the probability value of .000 ($p < 0.05$) is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore the hypothesis is rejected. This implies that provision of school plant facilities significantly predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings were done under the following headings

Inclusive education Programme and Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal four

Table 1 showed that inclusive education programme has a high positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four with 56.7%. The finding is in agreement with Loreman, McLeskey and Waldron (2021) that despite the potential of inclusive education programme, a significant gap exists in our understanding of how these programmes can be harnessed to drive progress towards SDG4. Moreover, there is a need to develop a more nuanced understanding of the critical factors influencing the success of SEPs and their alignment with broader educational and sustainable development objectives. Central to the SDG4 agenda is the principle of inclusive education, which emphasizes providing equitable access to quality education for all, without discrimination. The importance of inclusion in education is underscored by a substantial body of research.

For instance, the Global Education Monitoring Report (UNESCO, 2022) emphasizes the transformative potential of inclusive education, not only for students with disabilities but for society as a whole. Inclusive education has been found to enhance social cohesion, reduce inequalities, and

promote diversity (UNESCO, 2022). SEPs are designed to cater to the diverse learning needs of students with disabilities and to ensure their integration into mainstream educational settings (Loreman, 2019). SEPs have been widely recognized for their ability to provide tailored support, adapting teaching methods and curricula to meet the unique requirements of individual students.

Inclusive education Programmes (SEPs) are pivotal in addressing the diverse needs of students with disabilities and ensuring their integration into mainstream educational settings. SEPs are designed to provide tailored educational support, adapt teaching methods, and curricula to accommodate the unique requirements of individual students with disabilities (McLeskey & Waldron, 2021). These programmes not only aim to facilitate academic progress but also foster the holistic development of students by promoting their social and emotional well-being. One of the fundamental aspects of SEPs is the provision of individualized support. This tailoring of education to suit the specific needs of students with disabilities is achieved through the development of Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) in many educational systems. IEPs outline the goals, strategies, and necessary accommodations for each student, thereby ensuring that their unique learning needs are met. Therefore, hypothesis six showed that inclusive education programme significantly predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Provision of School Plant Facilities and Attainment of Sustainable Development Goal Four

Table 2 showed that provision of school plant facilities has a high positive prediction on attainment of sustainable development goal four with 38.5%. The finding is in agreement with Cardoso (2021) that adequate school plant encompasses a broad spectrum of elements, including safe and well-maintained classrooms, libraries, laboratories, playgrounds, sanitation facilities, and technological resources. These components not only affect the physical comfort of students but also impact their psychological and emotional well-being (Barrett, 2019). A welcoming and well-equipped school environment can foster a sense of belonging, motivation, and engagement among students, leading to improved attendance and overall academic performance (Rivkin, 2018).

The provision of adequate school plant also extends beyond the immediate educational context. It intersects with broader sustainable development objectives, contributing to environmental sustainability, community development, and economic growth (World Bank, 2018). Adequate school infrastructure can serve as a hub for community activities and as a safe haven in times of crisis (UNESCO, 2018). Furthermore, investing in school infrastructure stimulates job creation and the development of local economies, fostering social and economic stability.

A comprehensive assessment of school infrastructure across the globe reveals stark disparities. In many low-income and middle-income countries, a significant portion of schools lacks essential facilities such as clean water and sanitation, electricity, and functional classrooms (UNESCO, 2020). The Global Education Monitoring Report (2020) indicates that approximately 47% of schools in sub-Saharan Africa do not have basic water supply facilities, and 40% lack adequate sanitation. These deficiencies can be a deterrent to both students' attendance and their overall learning experiences. Sub-Saharan Africa represents a region where the inadequacy of school infrastructure is most pronounced. The lack of safe and well-maintained classrooms and sanitation facilities has detrimental effects on student retention and achievement (World Bank, 2019).

Moreover, the gender gap in education often widens in regions with poor school infrastructure. Girls, in particular, may be discouraged from attending schools that lack safe sanitation facilities, thus perpetuating gender inequality in education (Duflo, 2017). Therefore, hypothesis seven showed that provision of school plant facilities significantly predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, compensatory approaches such as free education for all, free transportation lead to the attainment of sustainable development goal four by 55.3 and 50.6% respectively. The hypotheses have revealed that all the variables significantly predicted attainment of sustainable development goal four in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proffered

1. Government should ensure that principals are monitored to manage their inclusive education programme for attainment of sustainable development goal four.
2. Principals should ensure that they adopt provision and maintenance of school plant facilities policies for attainment of sustainable development goal four

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